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EFFECTS OF GREEN PORT PRACTICES ON ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY OF NIGERIAN SEAPORTS.

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ABSTRACT

Maritime transport accounts for about 80% of global trade by volume and more than 70% by value, with ports serving as critical interfaces for international trade. Despite their crucial role in the global supply chain, it generates environmental externalities. This study adopted a survey research design, utilizing primary data collected through questionnaires administered to agencies and terminal operators at Apapa Port and Tin Can Island Port. A simple random sampling technique was employed. Data were measured using a five-point Likert scale and analysed using a multiple linear regression model to examine the relationship between selected environmental management practices and ISO environmental sustainability. The results indicate that: Reception facilities show a weak negative relationship with ISO environmental sustainability (coefficient = -0.093; p-value = 0.473). Use of electrically powered machines demonstrates a moderately weak but positive and statistically significant relationship (coefficient = 0.366; p-value = 0.009). Ballast water pollution prevention exhibits a moderate negative relationship (coefficient = -0.233; p-value = 0.11). Solid waste dumping and management reflects a very weak negative relationship (coefficient = -0.046; p-value = 0.755). Overall, only the use of electrically powered machines shows a significant positive correlation with ISO environmental sustainability. This implies that transitioning from diesel-powered equipment to electric-powered machinery makes a meaningful contribution to improving environmental sustainability in Nigerian seaports. Based on these findings, the study recommends that port authorities should provide adequate port-based reception facilities for ships operating within regional waters. Furthermore, the government should domesticate and

enforce stringent legislation mandating the proper use of reception facilities for the disposal of solid and liquid waste at Apapa and Tin Can Island Ports to strengthen environmental sustainability efforts.

KEYWORDS: Green port, Environmental Sustainability, Seaports, Green Practices

INTRODUCTION

The cornerstone of international trade and a major force behind globalization is maritime transport, which accounts for about 80 percent of global trade by volume and more than 70 percent by value (Chiu et al., 2014). Seaports handle seaborne trade, and as of 2018, 98,140 ships carried 11 billion tons of seaborne trade, and in 2019, ships weighing 100 gross tons or more made 4,362,737 port calls. Despite the worst shocks, especially the recent COVID-19 pandemic, ports and shipping remained at the forefront of global transportation, ensuring the continuous delivery of the world's medical supplies, food, energy, raw materials, manufactured goods, and components (UNCTAD 2020). Furthermore, ports improve and promote socioeconomic concerns by acting as a social keeper for workers and communities. More than 110,000 people work for 2200 port operators in Europe, loading and unloading ships as well as providing port-based services including logistics and warehousing (Van Hooydonk 2014; Alamoush et al., 2025). Despite its importance to the global supply chain, seaport operations pose a significant environmental risk due to their numerous interconnections, including cargo handling, vessel operations, hinterland transportation networks, industrial and semi-industrial operations, and energy production and distribution (Chiu et al., 2014; Notteboom et al., 2012). These externalities cause greenhouse gas emissions and contribute to climate change. Additionally, shipborne pollutants include solid waste, trash, and antifouling paints on ship hulls.

Onwuegbuchunam et al.,(2017), reported that ship-based pollution, such as ballast water, has a negative impact on the marine environment by introducing non-native species that endanger the sea animal population and negatively affecting the economies of nations that rely on commercial fishing. Despite the fact that oceans are essential to national and international economies because they provide jobs, food, and recreational opportunities, ports have an adverse effect on marine ecosystems and the oceans (Darbra et al. 2009). For instance, nearly 600,000 men and women directly depend on fishing and sectors associated to fishing, and the West African ecosystem's fisheries produce over 500 million euros a year (Kloff and Wicks, 2004).

Green port practices have evolved as a feasible strategy to address the environmental externalities resulting from port operations, development and growth, and industrial waste discharge. By combining eco-friendly technologies, renewable energy sources, and creative infrastructure designs, green ports deviate from the traditional model of port operations (Inal and Caglar, 2024). Furthermore, to reduce its ecological impact, a green port incorporates cutting-edge technologies, effective waste management systems, and renewable energy sources. Ports can greatly lessen their reliance on fossil fuels by utilizing wind, solar, and tidal energy. One concrete step toward sustainability is the Port of Rotterdam's pledge to use hydrogen as an energy source (Port of Rotterdam Authority, 2022; Lin et al., 2022; Bekesumowei et al., 2025). Such programs improve energy resilience in addition to reducing greenhouse gas emissions. It is thus essential

to put in place effective waste management systems. Recycling, composting, and waste-to-energy technologies must be given top priority in a green port. By actively participating in extensive recycling programs and striving for zero waste efforts, the Port of Barcelona is a prime example of best practices in trash reduction (Rolán et al, 2019). As a result of national governments' efforts to mainstream green economy principles and sustainable development goals, such as waste management policies, electric rubber-tired gantry cranes (ERTG), and port reception facilities for the treatment of ship-generated waste, the most important ports in the West and Central African sub-region such as Tema, Lagos, and Abidjan which account for nearly half of the region's total maritime trade in terms of volume also encountered the green port concept (Lawer et al., 2019). which are designed to make ports environmentally sustainable.

Port system has a significant environmental externality despite its substantial contribution to global economic growth through trade facilitation. The International Maritime Organization Greenhouse Gas Emission Study (2014) states that 796 million tons of CO₂ were released by shipping worldwide in 2012, accounting for 2.2% of total emissions that year. Maritime transportation was predicted to account for 15% of total CO₂ emissions by 2050 (Olukanni and Esu, 2018). Particularly in Nigeria, seaports lack an onshore power source that ships can use while docked (Anyanwu et al., 2022). This implies that ships at berth or while ducking release CO₂, NO_x, and SO₂ into the port environment, and port handling machinery runs on diesel, contributing to climate change, respiratory illnesses, and cardiovascular diseases. According to Onwuegbuchunam et al., (2017) Nigerian seaports' inadequate and poorly maintained reception facilities permit ships to release garbage into the ocean.

Through a global action plan, the Nigerian ports are dedicated to addressing the environmental externalities caused by port activities. Despite evidence of environmental contamination spanning ballast water discharge, air pollution, oil spills, etc., the majority of effort is directed toward developing sustainable marine and blue economic initiatives. Research on the environmental sustainability of Nigerian seaports is severely lacking. Few have evaluated the particular green initiatives that are now in effect. This study evaluates the impact of green port practices on the environmental sustainability at Apapa and Tin Can Island seaports in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study aims to close this gap. As opined by Ibrahim (2003), green port practices are a crucial idea for port firms' growth and operations in order to stop environmental damage, biodiversity loss, and the unsustainable use of natural resources. In addition, as green is usually associated with energy efficiency, the port and port authorities will gain a lot from implementing a green operation. eventually lower operating expenses for the participating port while simultaneously improving all operational and economic elements (Nazry, 2019). For example, Bremen ports have put in place a number of policies, technologies, and procedures in order to achieve the goal of being a green port. They have also offered a number of green practices to ships that call at their ports. The port authority has integrated environmental objectives into its planning and operating frameworks and established measures strategically. While on-shore power supply options for maritime

shipping are currently being evaluated, a total of 18 shore power connectors have been installed to ensure that inland vessels berthing at the port are powered by clean energy, allowing them to shut down their auxiliary engines that would have run on diesel generators. The power is generated from renewable sources for inland vessels that berth at the port and related port operations (Bremen Ports, 2016; Lawer et al., 2019). Additionally, diesel particulate matter, nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and sulfur oxides (SO_x) were significantly reduced as a result of the introduction of the Clean Air Action Plan (CAAP) by the Ports of Los Angeles and Long Beach (Anyanwu et al., 2025).

On the other hand, ports in developing nations deal with issues including scarce resources, poor infrastructure, and laxer environmental standards. Research conducted in Vietnam has demonstrated the possibility of developing green ports, highlighting the necessity of investing in cleaner technology and reforming policies (Le & Nyangu, 2023). The infrastructure required to receive and handle the garbage produced on board ships that call at respective ports has been installed at the ports of Tema in Ghana and Abidjan in Ivory Coast in accordance with Annexes 1 and 5 of MARPOL 73/78, the port of Tema has granted concessions to environmental service businesses to take ship garbage and handle it in an environmentally sustainable manner. Similar to how the ports of Abidjan and Tema use electrified rubber-tired gantry cranes (ERTG) for terminal operations to reduce emissions, the by-product of processing the oily waste from ships is sold as fuel for manufacturing and industrial businesses in the industrial enclave (Lawer et al., 2019). The World Bank indicated that using green practices in port operations can boost productivity, lower operating expenses, and increase competitiveness. through the incorporation of contemporary technologies into port logistics, such as electric cars, paperwork, and automated cargo handling systems. (World Bank, 2021).

Research on green port practices is beginning to appear in Nigeria through the implementation of green shipping practices more especially, green shipping policy, green shipping design, and green shipping facilities. Chima and Odior (2023) examined the environmental performance of shipping businesses. Although their study offers insightful information about sustainable practices in shipping operations, it only covers shipping businesses and falls short in addressing green practices at the port level. The policy framework for creating a green port at Warri Seaport was examined by Bekesuomowei et al. (2025) operations, environment, energy, safety and security, human resources, and clean energy are potential elements influencing appropriate port digitalization, according to the study, which used the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient for analysis. Without examining green port practices. This study concentrated on a framework to support the development of green ports as pollution inventories, particularly air pollution, are the subject of the majority of studies in Nigeria (Olukani and Esu, 2018; Jimoda et al., 2019; Onwegbuchunem et al., 2019; Anyanwu et al., 2025; Anyanwu et al., 2022).

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

- **Green port**

In recent years, the green port idea has had a big impact. Any contemporary port should adopt green port concepts by focusing on technological and environmental preservation. Bekesuomowei (2025) asserted that each port's greenness is determined by its unique characteristics. Both green and smart ports must be connected to one another as a single, systematic concept that was created using a systematic governance framework in order to produce an intelligent or smart port (Chio et al., 2021).

The combination of ecologically friendly port operations, management, and activities is known as "green port." Measures for the sustainability of "Green Port" implementation can be defined in a number of ways, including recycling and material reuse, the use of renewable energy in port operations and activities, and the adoption of pertinent legislation for the reduction of emissions into the atmosphere. (Badurina et al., 2017) claims. Reducing environmental impacts has become a top priority for port operations in recent years. According to Chiu et al. (2014), the port is viewed as a system made up of various components that all work together to create its environmental impact. Air pollution, noise pollution, water pollution, soil pollution, industrial waste water, resource consumption, and other environmental impacts can all be categorized under this heading. According to Klopott (2013), with a focus on Poland, the top ten environmental priorities of three Polish ports in 2012 were ballast water, ship exhaust emissions, noise, dust, dredging (disposal), port development (land), conservation areas, ship waste (sewage), energy consumption, and local community relations. In order to prevent environmental damage, biodiversity loss, and the unsustainable use of natural resources, the Green Port model is a crucial idea for the construction and functioning of ports. this aligns with the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development goal that calls for addressing climate change, cutting carbon emissions, and preparing for its effects. As previously stated, green ports also work toward the goal of protecting life below the water by putting policies in place to protect marine ecosystems and avoid pollution (Inal and Dere, 2024).

The majority of ports worldwide have adopted and implemented green port practices as a feasible choice and strategy. In Europe, Leixoes, Naples, and Valencia made investments in hydrogen and ocean energy; Hamburg, Antwerp, and Rotterdam made investments in wind energy generation; and Amsterdam, Genoa, and Antwerp made investments in sustainable energy generation (Munim and Saha, 2021). Because of their unwavering commitment to green port operations, a number of ports in East Asia, including the ports of Shanghai, Hong Kong, Singapore, Tokyo, and Busan, have received the Green Port certification (Teerawattana and Yang, 2019). Additionally, the ISO 14001 Environmental Management System is installed in nearly 63% of Croatian marinas (Jugović et al., 2022). Notable international organizations like the European Sea Ports Organization (ESPO), which has created green guidelines and standards of conduct for its ports, support green port initiatives. In West Africa, the non-governmental Ports

Environmental Network Africa (PENAf), and the regional secretariat of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) have recently launched an ambitious sustainability initiative. In North America, the Association of American Port Authorities (AAPA) offers a sustainability guide for its ports (AAPA, 2007).

- **Environmental Sustainability Practices at Seaports**

Environmental protection has gained international attention in recent years due to the world economy's rapid growth and the severity of climate change. The 13th Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which was endorsed by UN member states in 2015, focuses on mitigating climate change and lessening its effects on the environment (Shen et al., 2025). In this regard, environmental sustainability has emerged as a major force behind the solution of the world's environmental problems. In order to preserve ecological balance and safeguard ecosystems, environmental sustainability refers to the prudent use of the planet's resources to meet current requirements without endangering the ability of future generations to meet their own (Jaszczak, 2020).

Kaswan et al., (2019) argued that because of the need to protect ecosystems for future generations satisfying present demands shouldn't compromise environmental quality. Wastewater, exhaust gases, solid waste, and greenhouse gas emissions from the auxiliary engines of ships docked at ports are just a few of the major environmental externalities produced by construction activities and port operations at seaports that seriously endanger the surrounding environments (Li et al., 2024). Air pollution, which frequently results from rock extraction, construction, site cleanup, and dust from transportation operations, is one of the main environmental problems at ports. Similar to this, pollutants such sulfur oxides, nitrogen oxides, carbon monoxide, and particulate matter are released by ship traffic and cargo-handling machinery (Notteboom et al., 2020; Roh et al., 2016).

According to estimates, particulate matter and emissions from commercial ships are responsible for more than 60,000 deaths per year from lung cancer and cardiovascular disorders along the coasts of South Asia, Europe, and East Asia (Corbett et al., 2007). Sustainability methods have therefore become a practical way to guarantee eco-friendly and effective port operations in order to reduce these externalities.

Sustainability practices, according to Kang and Kim (2017), are collections of laws or programs intended to accomplish sustainable development objectives, guaranteeing that port activities do not negatively impact the environment while maintaining long-term economic and social well-being. In a similar vein, Tan et al. (2011) averred that, within the parameters of environmental rules, the use of sustainable practices promotes economic stability and enhances port performance. Gimenez et al. (2012) pointed out that social externalities that impact port vicinities and neighboring communities, like noise pollution, health issues, and safety hazards, are also addressed

by environmental sustainability strategies as such, the sustainable development of seaports and their surrounding environments depends on effective environmental management. It is therefore crucial to reinforce environmental management strategies and increase port authorities' awareness of environmental protection (Bouman et al., 2017). To encourage port-environmental coexistence, the European Sea Ports Organization (ESPO) introduced EcoPorts initiative, which focuses on environmental awareness and management development (Darbra et al., 2004; Shen et al., 2025).

In an effort to lower ship-related greenhouse gas emissions, European and Asian ports have embraced the Environmental Ship Index (ESI) (Lister et al., 2015).

Globally, a number of programs have been put in place to lessen environmental externalities. The ESPO Self-Diagnosis Method (SDM), the Port Environmental Review System (PERS), the European Union's Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS), and the EcoPorts initiative are noteworthy examples that integrate the general requirements of international environmental management standards like ISO 14001. Additionally, ports with ISO 50001 accreditation have addressed energy management and audits, including Antwerp, Valencia, Rotterdam, Genoa, Dover, and Livorno (ESPO, 2018). Major hub ports like Tema Port, Lagos Port, and the Port of Abidjan handle almost half of the amount of marine traffic in the West African subregion (Lawer et al., 2019).

To address transboundary environmental challenges and encourage environmentally sustainable port operations, these ports have implemented a number of environmental frameworks (UNEP, 2011). Environmental service providers have been hired by the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) to handle ship and port-generated garbage at the Lagos and Apapa Ports through a public-private partnership with African Circle Ltd. and Sea View Properties Ltd in accordance with MARPOL 73/78 Annexes I and V, the Port of Abidjan has set up sufficient port reception facilities to gather and handle garbage produced by ships. Similarly, a waste management strategy based on the 3Rs reduce, reuse, and recycle has been put into place by the Ghana Ports and Harbours Authority (GPHA) and Meridian Port Services (MPS), a significant container terminal operator. According to Lawer et al. (2019), this program has greatly decreased waste generation and boosted the economy. In addition, these ports have switched to electrified rubber-tired gantry cranes from conventional fossil fuel-powered ones in an effort to cut emissions. However, the Environmental Management Systems (EMS), which act as frameworks for methodical environmental management, have only been certified for the ports of Tema and Abidjan. These technologies are designed to avoid oil spills, manage effluent discharges, control water pollution, prevent hazardous waste dumping, and guarantee sustainable waste management at the port-ship interface. However, there hasn't been much improvement in the quality of the air (Lawer et al., 2019).

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a survey research design to collect data and conduct quantitative analysis on green port practices aimed at enhancing environmental sustainability in

Nigerian seaports. The adoption of this design was intended to capture the perspectives of key port stakeholders regarding the effects of green port initiatives on environmental sustainability within Nigerian seaports. A positivist philosophical approach was adopted for data collection and interpretation to achieve the study's objectives. According to Adenigbo (2024), the positivist approach provides a framework for generating reliable and objective knowledge through observation and supports the use of questionnaires for primary data collection and quantitative analysis. Data for the study were obtained from key stakeholders involved in operational and regulatory activities at the Apapa Port Complex, Lagos, Nigeria.

The Apapa seaport was selected as the study area because it is Nigeria's principal port, handling over 70% of the nation's cargo throughput. Consequently, it faces significant environmental challenges arising from intensive operational activities. Lawer et al. (2019) also described Apapa Port as a regional hub, accounting for nearly half of West Africa's maritime trade volume. The seaport is located in Lagos State, in the southwestern coastal region of Nigeria, at approximately latitude 6.6080°N and longitude 3.6218°E.

The study population comprised staff of the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA), Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA), Nigerian Shippers' Council (NSC), Integrated Logistics Services Limited (INTELS), and Greenview Development Nigeria Limited (GDNL).

Fig. 1: Map of Lagos State showing the Apapa Port Complex and Tin Can Island port
Source: Anyanwu et al. (2024).

A simple random sampling method was used to administer the questionnaire, which comprised two sections. The first section captured respondents' demographic information, while the second assessed the impact of green port practices on environmental sustainability. A five-point Likert scale was employed, with responses ranging from 1 to 5: NA (Not Agreed), LA (Least Agreed), FA (Fairly Agreed), A (Agreed), and HA (Highly Agreed). The questionnaire included 10 statements designed to evaluate environmental sustainability practices at Apapa Port. Data were analyzed using linear regression to examine the relationship between the dependent variable (environmental sustainability) and the independent variables, namely the use of reception facilities, electrically powered machines, ballast water pollution prevention measures, and facilities for solid waste disposal.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents for the Study

Respondents	Number of Response	% of
Nigerian Port Authority	40	19.9
Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency	45	22.4
Nigerian Shippers Council	12	5.9
Integrated Logistics Service Limited	54	26.9
Green View Development Nigeria Limited	50	24.9
Total	201	100

FINDINGS

This study identified sets of green port practices put forward by ESPO used to green assess the environmental sustainability of ports in Nigeria. The green practices are ballast water pollution prevention, facilities for solid waste dumping and management, use of electrically powered machines, and use of reception facilities. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to analyze the effects of the identified green port practices on the environmental sustainability Apapa port and Tin Can Island port, the output obtained was interpreted based on model summary, ANOVA and coefficient table.

Model summary shows how much of the variation in environmental sustainability explains by the regression model. Table 1 shows that the adjusted R-squared value = .097 which means 97% of the outcomes of the variation in environmental sustainability is explained by ballast water pollution prevention, facilities for solid waste dumping and management, use of electrically powered machines, and use of reception facilities. An

ANOVA test for the regression model indicated that the overall model has a weak correlation at (p-value = 0.404, 0.054) which is in this case, we can say that there is moderately weak correlation between ISO environmental sustainability and green port practices in Nigerian seaports. This suggests that, based on this sample, the set of independent variables collectively have moderate influence on environmental sustainability.

The result in table 1 indicate that reception facilities show a weak negative relationship with the ISO environmental sustainability having -0.093 with a p-value = 0.473, which mean reception facilities does not have a meaningful influence on the ISO. According to Onwuegbuchunam et al. (2017) reception facilities are made available in Apapa port and Tin Can Island port, but they are poorly managed. This is intended with Lawer et al. (2019) that the provision and management of port and ship generated waste in Nigerian seaport is outsourced to private pollution control company and there are no proper oversight function and monitoring to ensures the essence of the contract is achieved hence, indiscriminate dumping and disposal waste continue to prevail within the port environment.

Use of electrically powered machines indicate moderately weak, but positive relationship with dependent variable having a coefficient of 0.366 at p-value = 0.009, which is statistically significant. Implying that increased installation of electrically powered machines is associated with a significant increase in environmental sustainability, this result imply that few machines are electrified in Nigerian ports, which could be due to electricity grid experienced in the country as ports machines if electrified would require constant power supply and that a blackout can lead to huge loss and cost burden on the shippers, port authority and shipping companies. Lawer et al. (2019) electrified rubber-tired gantry cranes (ERTG) is adopted and practiced in Apapa and Tin Can Island port for terminal operations to reduce emissions. Aside community benefit, replacing diesel with electricity in Tin Can Island, and Onne could reduce annual emissions by about 40,000 tons of CO₂ by 2030 and fully electrifying container terminal could cut emissions by as much as 310,000 tons per year (APM Terminals, 2025). In South Korea, Bu-San port is ranked first in terms of greenness because of it changed from the diesel fuel which was a source of RTGC into electricity (Park & Yeo (2012).

Ballast water pollution prevention shows a moderate negative relationship with ISO environmental sustainability having a coefficient of -0.233 with a p-value = 0.111 therefore, ballast water pollution prevention does not significantly explain changes in ISO environmental sustainability at seaport in Nigeria this is attributed to lack of strict compliance with ballast water management legislation by shipping companies despite and lack of proper enforcement. This is in consonance with the findings of Nwigwe et al. (2022) that the majority of the ships in Nigeria operate within the African continent with lesser concern for the installation of Ballast Water Treatment Plant since most of the countries are not members of the International Maritime Organization (IMO) hence,

mandating shipping companies to comply with Ballast Water Management System become a challenge.

The provision of facilities for solid waste dumping and management reflects a very weak negative relationship with ISO environmental sustainability, and highly insignificant having a coefficient of -0.046, with a p-value = 0.755. This means that the adequacy of solid waste reception facilities in the port does not significantly enhance environmental sustainability as reception facilities are made available but not properly managed by the individuals or institution in charge. The port authority could not provide stringent regulations to ensure the facilities are well managed by the private companies in charge and also mandate every shipping line or terminal operators to comply or face grave penalty.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study provide a comprehensive assessment of the effects of green port practices on the environmental sustainability of at Apapa and Tin Can Island ports in Nigeria, revealing a moderate effects or correlation. Based on result of the analysis, ballast water pollution prevention, use of reception facilities, facilities for solid waste dumping have a moderately weak correlation or influence on Apapa and Tin Can Island port environmental sustainability, this is a result of poor legislation and management policy. Electrically powered machines show a significant positive correlation, the result imply that transitioning from diesel fuel power to electric power has a significant contribution to port environmental sustainability at seaport in Nigeria. In west African port like Ghana, onshore power supply is made available for vessel at berth, most terminal operators at Apapa and Tin Can Island port uses electric rubber-tired gantry cranes (RTGC).

These strategies have a momentous impact on port environment such as greenhouse gas emission reduction and mitigating climate change through reduction of sulphuric oxide SO_x carbon dioxide CO_2 , Nitrogen oxide NO_x and particulate matter (PM). Reducing air pollution, enhance environmental condition of the port and improve operational efficiency. Achieving environmental sustainability in port also enhance economic gain and social prosperity of the port. The use of random sampling method which give room for equal participation opportunity is subject to perceptual biases, which might affect the accuracy of the assessment of the effects of green port practices on environmental sustainability of Apapa and Tin Can Island ports.

Therefore, Green port practices play a momentous role in ensuring the sustainability of seaports and all aspect of port operations such as vessels operations, cargo handling activities, industrial water discharge, and hinterland transport system can be asses to achieve environmentally friendly operations for economic resilience and social prosperity.

- **Recommendations**

The following recommendation were made based on the findings of this study.

1. Port authority should provide port-based reception facilities for ships operating withing regional waters with low service charge as an alternative measure of complying with ballast water management policy.
2. Government should domesticate stringent legislation on the use of reception facilities and ensure the policy is well implemented and to monitor compliance of shipping lines.

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